

Uncertainty quantification in the volume reconstruction from stereo-DIC measurements using virtual experiments

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Abstract — To characterise and model the mechanical behaviour of metals up to large deformations, it is essential to understand the deformation in the material bulk. Although the adoption of full-field measurement techniques in material testing and characterisation is rapidly increasing, the technology is still limited to surface measurements. By employing stereo-DIC surface measurements, the internal mesh generation method is used to reconstruct the volume displacement field. The stereo-DIC measurements on the front and back surfaces of a flat specimen are replicated through two sets of synthetic images. Preliminary results show a good agreement between the positioning of reconstructed and reference internal points, highlighting the influence of the DIC measurement chain. However, the uncertainty quantification should also consider the strain field and will be extended to consider the effects of noise or DIC settings.

Keywords — Digital Image Correlation, Stereo-DIC, Volume Reconstruction, Virtual Experiments, Error Quantification

Introduction In the last two decades, the use of full-field optical techniques to measure the shape, motion and surface deformation of solids has considerably increased. This diffusion has allowed a wide development in material testing and characterisation, where the adoption of full-field measurement techniques is increasingly becoming the standard procedure [1]. Among these optical techniques, the digital image correlation (DIC) is one of the most widespread and fast-growing method, already used in many engineering applications [2]. Although the DIC has proved to be a very versatile and accurate technique, it is capable of measuring only surface shape changing (i.e. displacement fields) in the 3D space, failing to provide information in the bulk of the material.

From the surface measurements, Rossi et al. introduced the internal mesh generation (IMG) method to reconstruct the volume displacement field [3]. The proposed method has the potential to replace more advanced and costly techniques and also to overcome some of the main drawbacks of 3D-deformation measurement techniques such as the digital volume correlation on heterogeneous materials. Basically, starting from the 3D displacement fields measured on the specimen surface, the IMG method creates nodal points regularly distributed in the material bulk, by employing quadratic Bézier curves as interpolation functions. However, the method accuracy has yet not been extensively evaluated. In this work, the uncertainty associated to the IMG method coupled with DIC measured data is investigated through the use of virtual experiments [4].

Methods As depicted in Figure 1, the approach numerically reproduces a standard tensile test and the measurement chain associated to a stereo-DIC setup composed by four cameras. A 3D finite element model of a 20 mm thick flat specimen, with material characteristic of an aluminium alloy, is used to retrieve the displacement fields for deforming a reference speckle pattern according to the procedure described in [5, 6]. Thereby, two sets of synthetic images are generated, replicating the stereo-DIC measurement on the front and back surfaces of the specimen respectively. The DIC maps obtained with different setup configurations and produced with different correlation settings can be used to evaluate the best combination of analysis parameters by comparing the IMG reconstruction with the ground-truth provided by the FE input data.

Results The DIC measurements depicted in Figure 1 were obtained using the commercial software MatchID (www.matchid.eu, version 2021.2). The subset size and step size were set to 13 pixel² and 2 pixels respectively, to obtain approximately 47000 measurement points on each surface. The preliminary results do not consider noise, and a good agreement on the positioning of internal points is observed, with an average error of 0.24 mm (± 0.11 standard deviation). Also, the localized necking is observed in the thickness direction, validating the application of the IMG method.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the virtual experiment framework employed to quantify the error associated to coupling the IMG method to 3D-DIC measurements on numerically deformed images.

Discussion and Conclusion The IMG method has the potential to reconstruct the volume displacement based on surface measurements. Preliminary results show a good agreement between the reconstructed and reference internal points; however, this analysis will be extended to quantify the error induced in the reconstructed strain field. Additionally, the error analysis will consider the impact of different configurations, such as noise, subset size, step size, or mesh size.

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